

RELATIONS OF FAMILY AND SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF EDUCATION IN CHILD REARING

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Abstract: the article provides an overview of national research on the problem of relations between parents and children. The article also mentions that any family relationship between the younger and older, and what the dynamics observed in the study of the problems of this issue.

Keywords: family, relationships, parents, children, groups.

Problems of parents and children have always been an integral part of family relationships. At all times, disagreements arose between the older and younger generations. Therefore, the priority task of the state youth policy in the Russian Federation is the creation of favorable conditions for young families aimed at increasing the birth rate, the formation of family culture values and the image of a successful young family. In the works of modern researchers, one can see a diverse approach to the term "family". For example, Fomina L.K. connects the family with the most important value in the lives of many people [3]. "A family is a social group in which there is a subject with certain characteristics and an object of influence, which is also endowed with certain properties." The psychological aspect of family research is presented in the works of L. B. Schneider. "The family is the only social group that has adapted to the many successive events in such a small living space and within such a short time".

The sociological aspect of the study is presented in the works of A. G. Kharchev and M. S. Matskovsky. Family - this is a new object, with new properties, where the old properties of the family can mysteriously disappear. The family is first of all the relationship between its persons. To create a family means to build relationships of love, understanding and support. According to A. Kronik, the attitude of parents towards children is characterized by a gradual increase experiences of psychological intimacy. As children grow older, the attitude of parents towards them is experienced as more and more close.

The pedagogical direction in the study of family relations is associated with the name of Hansheinz Reinprecht. He tries to show that the driving force behind education is not an uncompromising struggle against evil, but love and understanding.

We conducted a sociological study under the guidance of T. V. Korosteleva on the topic "Parents and children". In a survey to study the socio-pedagogical aspects of child-parent relationships, the respondents were young people aged 16 to 30 years, in the amount of 103 people. Analysis of the results showed that the young people who were interviewed generally have an idea about the relationship between parents and children. On the first question: "What are the main causes of family conflicts?" we can say that in 10% - this is caused by distrust of each other; 14% of respondents - unsatisfied needs. But the main cause of conflicts in the family is communication with the opposite sex (60%), and a small proportion believe that selfishness is practically not the cause of the conflict situation. To the second question: "Do you often adhere to family traditions?" 30% answered - always; the smallest number of people said - quite often; 20% - rarely, and most of all (40%) were in favor of not adhering to family traditions. Based on the results of the third question: "Do children often spend time with their parents?" it was revealed that 30% of children spend a huge amount of time with their parents; 15% try to do it whenever possible; and 5% simply do not have time.

Most of the respondents do not want to be hostages of traditions and beliefs that have been handed down from time immemorial centuries, and many people are now alien to a long pastime with their parents (50%). Another subject of our research is the relationship between parents and children. An all-Russian survey was conducted, where 1600 people were interviewed in 130 settlements, in 42 areas in people 14 to 35 years old. The survey showed that family relations are friendly (22%), warm (17%), loving (30%). Every third believes that children and parents always find a common opinion, and every fourth believes that there are not even grounds for contradictions in families. The overwhelming majority also spoke in favor of children choosing their own specialty (86%), and not following in the footsteps of their parents. The conditions for conducting the methods in the control section did not change. As a result, data were obtained that testify to the effectiveness of the program to change attitudes in the minds of mothers. A quantitative analysis of the results showed that 60% of mothers, as a result of the program, changed their relationship style in the direction of socially desirable.

These mothers know their child, realistically assess his actions, respond adequately and flexibly to various situations, are able to take the position of the child, accept his point of view, are dialogic, understand and accept the child as he is. They are sensitive, often talk about the child, experience with him, are able to

protect him in any situation. One parent, which is 10% of the entire experimental group, maintains a symbiotic relationship with her son. It can be assumed that a severe psychotraumatic situation (divorce) in which a woman is in during the program, did not allow her to fully concentrate on her position as a mother, to realize the psychological attitudes towards her son with a disability. Therefore, taking into account the depth and constancy of the frustrating factor, a cycle of supporting individual (1, 2 times a month) and group sessions is necessary. In 30% of cases, a combination of several scales with a high percentage rank is preserved, which indicates an unstable type of education. Of the 30% of the unstable type of relationship: 10% are a combination of rejection - symbiosis - infantilization; 10% rejection - hypersocialization - infantilization; 10% symbiosis - hypersocialization - infantilization.

It should be pointed out that in the system of organizing work with youth, it is necessary to take into account the concept of preparing for upbringing in the family as the main basis for fruitful relations between parents and children.

Literature:

1. Korosteleva T. V. Economic activity and "money" behavior of student youth // Canada. 2012.
2. Federal Law "On State Youth Policy in the Russian Federation until 2025" (dated November 29, 2014 N 2403).
3. Fomina LK The concept and types of child-parent relationships // Young scientist. - 2014. S. 704-707.
4. Hansheinz Reinprecht. Education without regrets. M. 2000. S. 256.
5. Kharchev A. G., Matskovsky M. S. Modern family and its problems, M., 1993. P. 224.
6. Schneider L. B. Family: looking ahead. P. 2013. S. 368.

